

Design of a Semitransparent Dual-Mode Filter for Antenna Applications

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Abstract— A new dual-mode filter that allows the passage of most of the visible light is designed in this paper. The proposed filter is based on a square ring resonator that is perturbed by a square patch at its corner. The filter is designed using a metallic mesh that produces the effect of its metallic surfaces but has sufficient spacing to offer optical transparency greater than 75%. The manufacture of the filter through 3D printing allows the substrate to be eliminated, thereby reducing its insertion losses to 1.5 dB. The selective filter offers a flat passband frequency response with a 3 dB fractional bandwidth of more than 8% and rejection levels greater than 20 dB. This work allows the integration of this device together with optically transparent antennas to add filtering functionality to systems that require transparency due to their location.

Index Terms—Optically transparent, Dual-mode filter, Metallic grid, Passband filter.

I. INTRODUCTION

We are already witnessing the technological planning of future 6G networks. In which the growing bandwidth will be combined with a saturation of the radio spectrum and the overlap of the communications infrastructures necessary to implement paradigms such as Smart Cities or the IoT [1][2]. Taking advantage of the potential of next-generation wireless networks will be one of the keys that will determine critical antenna technologies and their associated electronics. In this context there are two important aspects that pose challenges that, although not new, will be aggravated in densely populated environments. On the one hand, the possible coverage problems of these networks, due to both the frequencies used and the inadequate transition between the outdoor and indoor communications systems of the buildings. On the other hand, networks and systems need sufficient locations, with an appropriate location from an electromagnetic point of view and that offer efficient and low-cost solutions. One of the locations that could be used are windows, glass surfaces and other transparent architectural elements of buildings and vehicles [2]. Of course, these offer large areas in which to place the antenna systems and with versatile and efficient locations. With the aim of allowing the placement of antennas in these windows while preserving natural lighting and reducing their possible visual impact as much as possible, optically transparent antennas have emerged [3]. There are numerous works that have been published in recent years in relation to transparent

antennas, including array systems[4] and MIMO applications [5][6].

This paper proposes an optically semi-transparent version of a compact planar filter known as dual-mode. This filter offers a bandpass response that is based on the control of dual modes in a ring resonator using a printed perturbation. The filter in microstrip technology has been described in detail in numerous works [7][8][9]. Typically, for frequencies around 2-3 GHz, the insertion losses of these filters are between 1.5-3 dB depending on their implementation, although recently low-loss solutions at higher frequencies based on inverted microstrip Gap Waveguide technology have been proposed [10]. These filters use a resonator that produces orthogonal modes, and through a printed perturbation it excites degenerate modes causing efficient coupling between the filter ports [7]. If there is no perturbation geometry or the size is not sufficient, the perfect symmetry of the resonator only allows orthogonal modes and only one of them will be generated at the input port due to the orthogonality with that on the other side of the resonator [9]. One of the main advantages of this filter is its compactness and high selectivity. It is now proposed to show the possibility of designing versions with sufficient transparency in the optical range (above 70%) to allow filtering the signal from a transparent antenna located nearby. These versions of optically transparent antenna and filter devices represent an advance in the use of window surfaces of buildings or vehicles for the effective deployment of new and improved 6G networks.

Fig.1. Scheme of the semi-transparent filter made using a metallic grid with its main geometric parameters: a) top view b) bottom view c) side view.

Furthermore, our proposal offers, through 3D printing of the metal layers consisting of a metal grid, the possibility of

implementing the filter without a substrate, which means a significant reduction in the losses of these potentially transparent elements. Fig.1 shows the metallic grid configuration of the bandpass filter presented in this paper. The filter consists of a square ring resonator with side a with a square perturbation (of size p) and placed in the corner of the ring. The idea is that all the metal parts of the filter are implemented using a metallized mesh small enough to offer an adequate electromagnetic response but that allows most of the visible light to pass through. The filter is fed by two meshed lines that allow the excitation of the sides of the resonator as seen in Fig. 1. The energy of the device is contactless coupled between a matching stub and each side of the ring. The essential geometric parameters to adjust the filter are shown in Fig. 1. These parameters control the response of the filter while others will remain fixed, such as the filter thickness h shown in Fig. 1 c), which in our case is proposed performed with an air layer of thickness $h=1.2$ mm, existing between the ground plane (Fig. 1 b) and the upper resonant element (Fig. 1a). Throughout the work, the CST Microwave Studio tool has been used for the electromagnetic analysis of the problem.

II. DUAL-MODE SEMITRANSSPARENT FILTER DESIGN

Mesh antennas are designed using traditional metal-based materials. Conductors (such as copper or silver) with stamped holes or spaces within the topology of the radiating element are typically used [2][3]. In this work it is proposed to use the same technique for the implementation of the filter layers, which allows the light to transmit through the gaps of the filter elements in this case. Fig. 2 shows the first model considered that uses a grid of 9×9 wire elements of width $d=0.8$ mm. This width based on previous experience with transparent antennas manufactured using 3D printing techniques allows adequate mechanical support and good electrical performance. For this reason, this width for the metallic grid wires remains constant throughout the work. The thickness of the metal wires of the mesh is $t=0.8$ mm for all the cases analyzed in the work. Finally, the ground plane has a square geometry, and its dimensions ($m_x=m_y=60$ mm) will also remain fixed in all the simulations shown.

Fig.2. Front view of the initial 3D model considered with a ground plane of 9×9 elements in the grid ($a=37.6$ mm and $b=33.6$ mm).

The relationship between the area occupied by the non-transparent parts of the antenna or filter with respect to the

surface of the element determines its level of transparency. It is expected that as we increase the transparency, the electromagnetic behavior of the device progressively deteriorates; in the case of antennas, a decrease in their gain has been experimentally observed [2]. A tradeoff between the electrical behavior of the device and its transparency guides the design, while on the other hand mechanical robustness and manufacturing restrictions apply.

A. Electromagnetic behaviour vs transparency

The simulation result for the first semitransparent filter described in Fig. 2 is shown in Fig. 3. This filter has a transparency slightly above 70% and achieves a flat passband centered at $f=2$ GHz with an 11% 3dB fractional bandwidth. The out-of-band rejection level is higher than -20 dB reaching two transmission zeros at 1.74 GHz and 2.36 GHz respectively. With the aim of increasing transparency, we have chosen in the following to implement the design with a grid of 7×7 elements for the ground plane. This configuration ensures transparencies greater than 70% and depending on the overlap between the lower and upper layers of the filter, transparency levels greater than 75% can be achieved.

Fig.3. Simulated filter response with 9×9 grid elements ($a=37.6$ mm, $b=33.6$ mm, $p=6.5$ mm, $g=1.7$ mm, $s=2$ mm).

B. Dual-mode filter geometry: size and perturbation

In this type of dual-mode filters, the size of the ring sets the possible operating frequency, while the length of the square perturbation allows adjusting the splitting of the degenerate modes that will enable energy coupling between ports [7]. The frequency chosen for the filter is 2 GHz, considering that the size of the ring, $(a+b)/2$ in Fig. 1) must have an approximate value of $\lambda/4$ and assuming the propagation in air (the substrate is the air layer between the resonator and the ground plane). The dimensions for the resonator at these frequencies are close to 37.5 mm [7][9].

The configuration with orthogonal feeds and a square patch perturbation produces a quasi-elliptical function with two transmission zeros on the sides of the passband [8], as shown in Fig. 4. Fig. 4 shows the simulated response for two filters of similar parameters in which the ring dimension changes slightly, from 41 mm to a size of 40 mm to center the response at 2 GHz. The graph shows how the frequency of the passband is controlled by the dimensions of the ring. In this case the dimension of the center of the ring is 37 mm,

which is slightly smaller than the theoretical size expected for the resonator.

Fig.4. Response of the proposed filter with 7 x 7 grid for two sizes of the resonator ring ($b=34$ mm, $p=6.8$ mm, $s=2.1$ mm and $g=1.75$ mm).

The square patch used as a perturbation drives dual-mode operation for the bandpass filter. It is a key design element that affects insertion losses, return losses and filter bandwidth [7][10]. In Fig. 5 the filter responses for different dimensions of the perturbed patch are shown. A minimum size for the stub perturbation p in the ring is necessary to obtain an adequate elliptic function operation. In this case, the values of the stub (p) between 6.5-7.5 mm increase resonance frequency splitting for the modes to obtain an improved bandwidth and a better matching.

Fig. 5. Simulated S parameters for different filters in which the size of the perturbation p is varied ($a=40$ mm, $b=34$ mm, $s=2.1$ mm and $g=1.75$ mm)

It can be concluded from the analysis carried out in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 how it is possible to adjust the response of the filter in the appropriate band by varying the dimensions of the ring resonator, both its average dimension $(a+b)/2$ and its width $(a-b)/2$. On the other hand, the size of the perturbation produces the splitting of the modes and sets the passband.

C. Coupling gap

One of the parameters that most affects the energy coupling in the filter is the gap between the matching feeding line and the ring [8]. On one hand if the gap is too large poor coupling occurs, on the other hand, if the gap is very small, it modifies the electromagnetic field distribution of the resonator. When this occurs, the matching of the device worsens and the degenerate modes partially lose their symmetry, which deteriorates the response of the filter, significantly worsening the insertion losses. In Fig. 6 it can be seen how this lack of symmetry and loss of efficiency in

the coupling occurs for gaps below 1.5 mm. The simulations show how in the proposed configuration a gap between values 1.8 mm and 2.2 mm produces an effective coupling and preserves symmetry, obtaining reduced insertion losses as can be seen in Fig. 6. The width (s in Fig. 1) of the coupling stub in which ends the matching feeding line does not have a very significant effect on filter's response for values between 1.5 mm and 3 mm, we have chosen to simplify and consider values close to $s=2$ mm in most cases.

Fig.6. Simulated S parameters as a function of the gap between matching feeding lines and the ring ($a=40$ mm, $b=34$ mm, $s=2$ mm and $p=7$ mm).

III. FILTER PERFORMANCE AND MANUFACTURING WITH 3D PRINTING TECHNIQUE

This section provides some results obtained by the filter and design considerations specific to the 3D printed manufacturing method. After adjusting the geometric parameters, the simulated center frequency is 2 GHz, the 3 dB fractional bandwidth is 8.5% from 1.92 to 2.09 GHz. Fig. 7 shows two transmission zeros at 1.76 GHz and 2.29 GHz respectively. The S_{11} is below -10 dB between the frequencies of 1.92 GHz and 2.06 GHz. Finally in Fig. 7 we can see that the out-of-band rejection level for the filter is below -20 dB in the band of interest and 0.94 dB insertion losses are obtained at 2GHz. Considering the relationship between the surface occupied by the metallic grid elements, ground plane and filter, and the total surface of the device the level of optical transparency obtained by the proposed filter is close to 75%. There is no doubt that this typology allows transparencies above 70%. This level is sufficient for the use of architectural windows and vehicle windows as locations for radiant devices and their electronics.

Fig.7. Simulated S-parameters for the proposed semitransparent filter ($a=40$ mm, $b=33$, $p=6.9$ mm, $g=1.85$ mm and $s=2$ mm).

A. Filter operation and E-field distributions

In this section we will briefly illustrate the basic behavior of the designed filter using the field distributions obtained in the full-wave simulations. Firstly, it is observed in Fig. 8 how the modes for the zeros in the transmission band are completely orthogonal respectively to the port from which they are excited. For the frequency of the first transmission null that occurs at $f=1.75$ GHz, it can be seen in Fig. 8a) and Fig. 8d). While the non-transmission that occurs at the 2.3 GHz frequency can be verified through the orthogonality in the modes shown in Fig. 8c) and Fig. 8f). Secondly, it can be seen in Fig. 8b) and Fig. 8e) how at the work frequency, $f=2$ GHz, the resonator excites two slightly symmetrically rotated modes and degenerate frequency that enable efficient energy coupling as has been shown in the previous sections.

Fig.8. Ez electric field component calculated for three frequencies in the filter, for the excited modes of the two excitation ports of the device.

The perturbation in the resonator symmetry, in the form of a square patch in the ring corner, controls the generation of two degenerate modes whose split frequency produces the signal coupling between ports. If the perturbation is too small or does not exist, the generated modes are essentially orthogonal due to perfect rotation symmetry and do not couple energy.

Fig.9. Simulated Ez-field component for the semitransparent proposed filter at a frequency of $f=2$ GHz in the operation band.

To conclude the discussion on the physical operation of the filter, it should be noted that despite its implementation with a metallic mesh, the filter offers a typical elliptical response based on the generation of two degenerate modes (dual-mode) as can be clearly seen in Fig. 9. It is worth highlighting the configuration with the metallic grid that allows the passage of most of the visible light by more than

75%. This was the objective of the proposal that offers a combined use of the filter with transparent antennas for the adequate control of interference in new applications in which optical transparency could be a requirement.

B. Air or Lexan substrate: losses and manufacturing

This section discusses the effects on filter manufacturing, keeping in mind our previous experience with semi-transparent antennas. We have manufactured antennas with a similar grid, using 3D printing with a non-conductive plastic filament. In a second stage, this structure has been metalized with silver paint (with a 50% proportion of silver particles). The losses in said structure have been well characterized by an effective decrease in the conductivity of the metal with respect to copper and considering the roughness of the 3D printed surface (with rms of the order of 0.025). In this last section, this information has been taken into account to calculate the orders of magnitude of the losses associated with the filter according to the model used. On the other hand, until now manufacturing without a dielectric substrate of the filter (with a layer of air) had been taken into account, but there is the possibility of using a dielectric substrate that is optically transparent. This last possibility will now be considered and another filter with the same band has been designed but using a commercial transparent plastic substrate called Lexan whose electrical characteristics are $\epsilon=2.8$ and $\tan\delta=0.0025$.

Fig.10. Simulated filter response for different possible manufacturing cases, considering air as substrate and two real metals compared to PEC and using a commercial Lexan type dielectric substrate.

The Fig. 10 shows the simulated results for the three air filter cases, like those analyzed in the previous section. But in this case, the different metals used in its implementation are compared, copper or silver paint, with the ideal PEC case. The case with commercial dielectric substrate is different given that as the permittivity varies its dimensions change. In this case, to center the frequency in the same band, the main dimensions of the filter would be $m_x=m_y=50$ mm, $a=28.5$ mm, $b=23.5$ mm and $p=5$ mm. The insertion losses observed in Fig. 11 for the center frequency of the passband vary from 0.85 dB for the ideal PEC case, up to 0.98 dB for the case simulated with copper and a 1.3 dB losses level for the model 3D printing with silver paint. At another magnitude are the losses associated with the case with Lexan substrate, which increase up to 2.5 dB of return losses at 2 GHz, due to the real metal modelling with silver

paint and the losses associated with the plastic substrate. This last value is like that obtained in other dual-mode filter designs in microstrip technology for frequencies between 1-2 GHz.

Fig.11. Zoomed detail of the insertion losses calculated in the filter passband for the same cases analyzed in Fig. 10.

Although the filter could not be manufactured yet, a photograph of 3D printed ground planes of similar sizes is shown in Fig. 12. With the intention of showing the high levels of transparency that can be achieved with low-cost manufacturing techniques and that potentially offer an interesting line of new applications based on optically transparent devices integrated with antennas.

Fig. 12. Photograph of one of the first prototypes of the ground plane, placed on a window, with a similar level of transparency made using 3D printing

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper has described the procedure followed to design a dual-mode filter that allows the passage of most of the light in the optical range. The filter is based on the excitation of a ring resonator and the control of the degenerate modes that are produced by a square perturbation located in the corner of the ring. All the metal parts of the filter have been implemented by means of a metallic grid equivalent to the conductive surfaces but with sufficient gaps or spacing to allow its optical transparency by more than 75%. The filter offers a 3 dB fractional bandwidth of 8.5% centered at a frequency of 2 GHz. It offers high selectivity, adequate rejection level greater than 20 dB, a flat frequency response and low insertion losses of around 1.5 dB in its low-cost implementation through 3D printing and metallization techniques. These losses are essentially due to

the metal parts of the filter since its configuration allows it to be made without a substrate, although in another configuration it has also been integrated with a commercial transparent Lexan plastic that offers similar transparency and limited losses of the order of 2.5 dB. The new semi-transparent filter can be used to effectively control interferences in integrated systems along with antennas and arrays that require the passage of natural light.

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